

EFFORTS TO INCREASE THE TOURISM POTENTIAL OF SAMARKAND CITY

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***Abstract:** In this article, information is given about the efforts to increase the tourism potential of Samarkand city, the information about Samarkand's transformation into a tourist center in the next few years.*

***Keywords:** tourism, cooperation, monuments, historical places, UNESCO, road map, hotel, Great Silk Road, European Union, festival, tourist.*

The tourism sector is currently developing as one of the most important sectors of the economy. Uzbekistan, located in the heart of Central Asia, attracts the attention of tourists from all over the world every day. It is formed in the blood and historical memory of peoples and is manifested in their practical work. That is why he is powerful. "Preserving, studying and passing down the historical heritage from generation to generation is one of the most important priorities of our state policy." These sentences were not emphasized by the leader of our country for nothing. No matter how many years or centuries pass, some things in society and the attitude towards them will change, but the attitude towards the historical monument, our historical heritage, and our history in general will never change. In particular, the tourism potential of Samarkand is increasing day by day as we visit the historical monuments in Samarkand. No matter what country or region you are in, if you say that you are from Samarkand, you will surely be interested in the historical

monuments and buildings of Samarkand. has been the polish of the earth. In 2001, at the 25th session of UNESCO held in Finland, Samarkand was included in the World Heritage list of architectural and historical monuments as a city of intersection of cultures⁸. After extensive reconstruction work was carried out in the area, 1105 archaeological, 670 architectural, 37 places of interest, 18 monumental, 21 memorial In this regard, there are a total of 1851 material and cultural heritage objects⁹ it was shown how high the possibilities are. This is a proof that Samarkand is a region rich in cultures. Considering the number of cultural heritage sites located in Samarkand region, there are 966 archaeological, 286 architectural, and 16 monumental art monuments in Samarkand region, i.e. 19 archeological, 3 architectural in Bulung'ur district, 47 archeological in Ishtikhan district, 10 architecture, 36 archeology in Jomboy district, 5 architecture, 32 archeology in Kattakorgan district, 54 architecture, 26 archeology in Narpay district, 12 architecture, 45 archeology in Nurabad district, 5 architecture, 65 in Okdarya district archeology, 8 architecture, 147 archeology in Pstdargom district, 3 architecture, 30 archeology in Pakhtachi district, 9 architecture, 88 archeology in Payariq district, 6 architecture, 41 archeology in Koshrabot district, 3 architecture , 97 archeology, 32 architecture in Samarkand district, 58 archeology, 15 architecture in Toyloq district, 233 archeology, 58 architecture in Urgut district, 2 archeology, 63 architectural monuments in Samarkand city, a total of 1268¹⁰ cultural heritage sites are located. Today, some effective work is being done to preserve our cultural heritage.

In particular, to ensure high-level preparation and holding of the 25th session of the General Assembly of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) in September 2023, hosted by the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the events within its framework, as well as the city of Samarkand "2024 Economic Cooperation The Cabinet of Ministers

⁸ MEMORIALS OF SAMARKAND Sh. Kulmatov, A. Berdimuradov. - Samarkand: Iknam Bukhari International Center, 2017.5 p

⁹ G. Sirocheva "SAMARKAND - GEM OF THE EAST" GOLDEN BRAIN ISSN: 2181-4120 VOLUME 1 | ISSUE 9 | 2023

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¹⁰ Objects of cultural heritage "Samarkand region" T. 2016, p-15

decides to present the organization as a candidate for the status of "tourism capital"¹¹. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs was instructed to approve the "road map" for the promotion campaign "Samarkand - the tourism gate of New Uzbekistan"¹² and to increase the flow of tourists to Samarkand. But there is something in the development of tourism there are also shortcomings. For example, there are fewer separate buses for tourists from abroad, solving the problem of wf in tourist areas is the first issue. If we relax the tourism sector, tourism will develop day by day. In accordance with the strategy of developing tourism infrastructure in Samarkand, which will become a million city in the future, it is planned to increase the number of hotels to 163, the number of guest houses to 472, and the number of craft and souvenir shops to 459 by 2025¹³. Samarkand is one of the leading regions in domestic tourism. Since the beginning of the year, Samarkand - 900,000, Fergana - 850,000, Andijan - 650,000 domestic tourists have been leading the way in receiving domestic tourists. The president noted that the results of some regions, districts and cities are not good. In particular, 151,000 domestic tourists visited Syrdarya, 262,000 Navoi, and 275,000 Jizzakh¹⁴. It was noted that the new airport, 8 hotels, a congress hall, a park, and other entertainment and recreation complexes built in Samarkand should be used for Uzbeks and foreign tourists.

The "Great Silk Road" Samarkand tourism center, established at the initiative of the President, is increasing the flow of tourists. Now it is planned to turn Samarkand into the "Tourism Gate" of Uzbekistan and to increase the volume of tourist services by 10 times in the future¹⁵. In particular, the promotion campaign "Samarkand - the tourism gate of New Uzbekistan" demonstrating the tourism potential of Samarkand and the possibilities of the Samarkand International Airport will be launched in the

¹¹ <https://lex.uz/docs/-6401230>. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 98 dated 07.03.2023

¹² <https://www.spot.uz/oz/2022/10/17/samcity/> 42 organizations in Samarkand will be moved outside the city

¹³ "Yangi Uzbekiston" newspaper December 31 issue of the Doctor of Philosophy in Economics Jasur Umurzakov —Cities of millions!: Samarkand is a world-recognized international tourism metropolis, and Namangan is an industry, entrepreneurship, is becoming a regional center in the fields of education and culture!

¹⁴ <https://www.spot.uz/oz/2022/09/20/tourism/> Increasing the number of international and domestic flights, safari and pilgrimage tourism,

license requirements for travel agents being revoked, etc

¹⁵ <https://samaokb.uz/ya/1178-samarkand-in-2023-is-recommended-to-visit-one-of-13-destinations-in-the-world-done.htm>

regions of the republic and in foreign countries, and tourism information centers will be established to provide services to tourists. Preparations are underway for the next 25th session of the UN World Tourism Organization General Assembly in 2023 to be held in Samarkand.

According to the "Roadmap" project for the implementation of the development strategy in 2022, the decisions of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis and the Legislative Chamber on this issue will be developed in August. Other practical work will be carried out based on this decision. Also, next year, the city of Samarkand will be "European Union - Central Asia" is expected to host an international ministerial conference on strengthening interdependence and sustainable development. In general, by turning Samarkand into a "Tourism Gate", the volume of tourism services will be increased at least 110 times in the next five years, and 40,000 people will be employed in the sector¹⁶.

For this purpose, it is planned to establish more than 170 new hotels and family guest houses, to increase the number of beds to 19 thousand. Also, the International Culinary and Service School will be established, and leading restaurateurs from France, Japan, and Turkey will be involved in the training.

An international gastronomic festival will be organized in the region, and the number and geography of flights will be increased by attracting new foreign carriers to the international airport here.

¹⁶ <https://sv.zarnews.uz/post/samarkand-when-will-the-city-of-a-million-people-be-born>